

STUDY OF ANIMALS SYMBOLISM OF HUMAN TRAITS IN CHINESE ZODIAC

Deepika Bansal¹ and Mahesh Kumar Mishra²

¹Department of Design Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India, 2021

²Assistant Professor, Department of Design, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India 2021

Abstract

This is study of the 12 Chinese zodiac signs based upon the study of animals. Each of the 12 animals is symbolic of certain trait of their own which in China is believed to affect a person's personality and destiny. Here we are studying the origin of the Chinese zodiac, symbolism of each of the 12 animal and their relevance in today's time.

Introduction

The Chinese lunar calendar goes back to second millennium BC. Unlike western calendar where the years are progressively numbered (after Christ birth), the Chinese calendar is cyclic. Each cycle is of 12 years and then repeated after completion, starting from February and ending in January. Each year is represented by an animal (rat, ox, tiger, rabbit, dragon, snake, horse, goat, monkey, chicken, dog and pig) hence making them zodiac animals. Each animal is associated to a certain trait of human personality.

According to Chinese people the animal ruling one's birth year can deeply affect his/her life in terms of personality, behaviour, luck, career, love life, health and lifestyle. According to legends this animal lies in one's heart.

The Chinese Zodiac Sheng Xiao or Shu Xiang includes 12 animals in order of rat, ox, tiger, rabbit, dragon, snake, horse, goat, monkey, chicken, dog and pig representing each year in 12-year cycle, plays an essential role in Chinese culture.

Animal symbolism of human traits in Chinese Zodiac holds relevance in a person's life. There is a wide-spread belief in China that these animals have their own natural features and living habits which reflects in the traits of person born year. Their destiny and fates are also affected by them.

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

Methodology

This research is based on qualitative data which uses the secondary data for research. Secondary data is collected from online mediums such as Research Gate, Google Scholars for research paper and books from pdf drive.

Origin of Chinese Zodiac

The Chinese Zodiac, also called Sheng Xiao or Shu Xiang, features 12 animals in the order of: Rat, ox, tiger, rabbit, dragon, snake, horse, goat, monkey, rooster, dog and pig. Each of the animals represents a year of 12- year cycle, a day of 12 days cycle and 2 hours of 24 hours of a day.

Source: www.astrologycircle.com/chinese-

Originated almost 2000 years ago the records from excavated bamboo books prevails the existence of Chinese Zodiac before the Qin Dynasty (25-220AD). They first appeared in Zhan Guo period (5th century BC) and their exact date of creation is unknown. However, they were officially identified during the Han Dynasty (557-581AD).⁽⁷⁾

According to legend, Lord Buddha determined the 12 -animal zodiac of Chinese astrology. Before departing the earth Lord Buddha invited all the animals to come to him. Only 12 animals showed up to bid him farewell and as a reward he named a year after each animal in the order they arrived. The first animal to arrive was talkative rat, followed by hardworking ox, active tiger, detached rabbit, outspoken dragon, philosophical snake, energetic horse, artistic goat, irrepressible monkey, candid rooster, watchful dog and lastly resigned pig.⁽⁶⁻⁷⁾

According to another interesting legend about origin of Chinese zodiac. The Jade emperor wanted 12 animals as his palace guard. He organized a race for them where they had to cross a rapid current river and reach the finish line situated on the shore. Originally there was a cat and rat who hated each other. They were worst swimmers and hence decided to take help of generous ox and cross the river on his back. But rat was resolute to win hence pushed cat in the river, thus wasn't included in the race. Other variation is that rat never told cat about the race and hence never competed. After crossing the river, the clever rat jumped off ox's back and made it to first position. Ox came second followed by tiger; last position was stood by pig as he took food break. Each animal acquiring its year are

Source: hutong-school.com

symbolic to nature and characteristics of person born in that animal's year. ⁽¹²⁾

Source: Pinterest

RAT – shǔ(鼠)

Year: 1912, 1924, 1936, 1948, 1960, 1972, 1984, 1996, 2008, 2020, 2032

Rat the first zodiac of Chinese astrology is noted for its charm, creativity and survival. They use charm to deflect unpleasantness whenever possible. They are vigorous in nature and can adapt themselves to different circumstances. They have ability to be unseen as they dwell a private world which is veiled from the view. They are fascinating and talkative generally the spirit of any party. However, they are essentially introverted by nature and are most comfortable to socialize with close friends and family. They are wonderful friends and partners with easy going personalities. ⁽¹²⁾

The Rat is hardworking and intelligent which allows them to set clear goals in career and life. They are resourceful, ambitious, prefer to use their brains over

manual labor and are generally financially successful. There is good analytical and observant ability gives them an upper hand in a verbal battle of wits. According to Chinese folk legend, with maturity the rats are acquiring prophecy. They are always seeking new information and their exceptional knowledge helps them to bring up unique ideas, likewise they are natural teachers and like to impart knowledge to other people. Thriftiest of all zodiacs, every expenditure is carefully considered justified by the. They generally live a stable and prosperous life. ⁽⁶⁾

People born in rat year are physically attractive throughout their lives. They soul are warm hearted, passionate and live for the moment. They are always in pursuits of new adventures and love travelling to explore new and unusual things. They hate agendas, pressure and mundane routines.

In contrast to their good qualities' rats can sometimes be secretive, self-centered and witty. They are difficult to please and are highly critical of others. There profiteering and opportunistic behaviour can sometime reach to most unproductive form. Expressed in darkest form, rat's energy can be directed towards restlessness, dishonesty, agitation, aggressiveness and isolation. ⁽⁶⁾

Favourable Career:

People born in rat year make excellent business owners, shopkeeper, entrepreneur, teacher, politician, musician, scientist, philosopher, artists, author, singer, commercial traveller, criminologist and detective. ⁽⁶⁾⁽¹²⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Dragon, Ox, Rabbit

Chinese Zodiac Rats

Years of the Rat:
(If born then, you're a Rat.)

... 1924, 1936, 1948, 1960, 1972, 1984, 1996, 2008, 2020...

Lucky numbers	Lucky colors	Lucky flowers	Lucky directions
2, 3 and numbers containing them (like 23 and 32)	blue, gold, green	lily, African violet	west, northwest and southwest
Unlucky numbers	Unlucky colors	Unlucky directions	
5, 9 and numbers containing them (like 59 and 95)	yellow, brown	south and southeast	

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

Famous Personalities:

Some well-known people born in rat year are William Shakespeare (author), Claude Monet (painter), Katy Perry (singer), President George Washington (politician), Zubin Mehta (musician), Galileo Galilei (scientist), Prince Harry (Duke of Sussex).

OX –niú (牛)

Year: 1913, 1925, 1937, 1949, 1961, 1973, 1985, 1997, 2021, 2033

The second position of Chinese zodiac is stood by the ox, which is symbolic of strength and perseverance. They are used in agricultural activities which attach them to being tough, diligent and hardworking. They take slow actions after a long and persistent planning to which they apply their strong faith and tireless work, once plan is set, they can overcome any difficulty. As a result, ox people enjoy great success and stable life. ⁽¹¹⁾

In China, Ox is also symbolic of undivided parental love because of the tenderness by which they nurture their calves. Female oxen are deeply attached to their family and children. Oxen parents give much affection, practical care and self-sacrifice for their children. Male ox with their inborn authority and strong determination makes them credible and patriotic leaders. They have strong ambitions in life with sheer stubbornness and great patience they can survive adversities to achieve their goals. This incredible endurance of surviving the hardships has kept their families and nation bonded together. They are not influenced much by the surroundings, prefer to do things according to their ideals and compatibilities hence cannot be swayed easily. ⁽⁶⁾

Smart and responsible, stable and committed walk straight in their paths of life and understand importance of doing things correctly and honestly. They are down to earth and require direct connection with nature. They are known for their great gardening skills and love for nature. Also, they tend to protect the weak, small and helpless showcasing

Chinese Zodiac Oxes

Years of the Ox:
(If born then, you're a Ox.)

... 1913, 1925, 1937, 1949, 1961, 1973, 1985, 1997, 2009, 2021...

Lucky numbers
1 4
and numbers containing 1 and 4 (like 14 and 41)

Lucky colors
white
yellow
green

Lucky flowers
tulip
peach blossoms

Lucky directions
north, south

Unlucky numbers
5 6
and numbers containing them (like 56 and 65)

Unlucky colors
blue

Unlucky directions
southwest

Lucky Things: (smiley face icon)

Unlucky Things: (sad face icon)

their merciful nature.

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

In contrast to their good qualities, ox can be overly strict, and short-tempered. They hate to be opposed and fail which makes them overly authoritarian and rigid. They cannot stand any kind of disloyalty and are prone to hold long time grudges. They are not good communicators and hence fail to express their emotions.

Expressed in darkest form, they can be stubborn, possessive, revengeful and jealous. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favorable Career:

Blessed with excellent skills and talented hand they can succeed being a craftsman, gardener, artisan, painter, farmer, architect, archeologist, surgeon, chef. They can also be police officers, political leaders, military strategist, politician and lawyer. ⁽⁶⁾⁽¹²⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rat, rooster, snake

Least compatible: Tiger, horse, dragon, goat

Famous Personalities:

Some famous people born in ox year include; Barak Obama (politician), Princess Diana of Wales, Jawaharlal Nehru (politician), Charlie Chaplin (comedian), Adolph Hitler (dictator), Vincent Van Gogh (painter), Sachin Tendulkar (Cricketer).

TIGER – Hǔ (虎)

Year: 1914, 1926, 1938, 1950, 1962, 1974, 1986, 1998, 2010, 2022, 2034

The third position of Chinese zodiac is stood by the tiger are symbol of power, unwavering courage and lordliness. People born in Tiger year are known for their noble, authoritative, brave nature with strong moral and belief system. High self-esteem makes them independent and asocial. Their competitive nature seeks challenges and is resolute in achieving their career goals. They are natural leader, endowed with great confidence that is respected by others. Likewise, they enjoy high positions with authority and control. ⁽¹²⁾

The fiercely self-resilient tiger may look tough from outside, yet they are tender

Chinese Zodiac Tigers

Years of the Tiger:
(If born then, you're a Tiger.)

... 1914, 1926, 1938, 1950, 1962, 1974, 1986, 1998, 2010, 2022...

Lucky Things:

Lucky numbers: 1, 3, 4 and numbers containing them (like 13 and 43)

Lucky colors: blue, gray, orange

Lucky flowers: yellow lily, cineraria

Lucky directions: east, north, south

Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers: 6, 7, 8 and numbers containing them (like 67 and 87)

Unlucky colors: brown

Unlucky directions: southwest

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

hearted and affectionate towards they love. Hence, they are sensitive, deep thinkers and capable of great sympathy. Moreover, they are adventurous, energetic and ambitious people who reject the mundane and explore the unforeseen and unknowns. They are known for frequent changes in residences and jobs. They love socializing, going to parties and are the charms of any party. Eager to please, lively and sociable, there is something attractive and unique about their personality that entices others.

They temp fate, take chances and fight for noble ideals with strong sense of justice. They are devoted to their friends and family and stand by through their hard times. They may not prepare of anything but can handle situations well. ⁽⁶⁾⁽¹²⁾

Apart from their good qualities, tigers can be careless, hyperactive and undisciplined which can result in hasty actions without analysis. Their over authoritative nature can make them extremely short-tempered, rebellious and bossy. They are prone to quarrel with others when crossed. Expressed in the darkest form tigers can be arrogant,

jealous, aggressive, impulsive and seek thrill to point of injuries. ⁽⁶⁾

Favourable Career:

Tigers like anything in which they have leadership; they don't take orders and excel as boss, managers, and owners. Economist, politician, adventurer, public services, stunt persons, military head, actor and revolutionary. ⁽⁶⁾⁽¹²⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Dragon, Horse, Pig

Least compatible: Ox, Snake, Monkey

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in tiger year are; Tom Cruise (actor), Queen Elizabeth II, Tenzing Norgay (explorer), Steve Irwin(naturalist), Narendra Modi (politician), Leonardo di Caprio (actor), Usain Bolt(runner), Fidel Castro(Cuba revolutionary), Marilyn Monroe (Actress).

RABBIT – tù (兔)

Year: 1927, 1939, 1951, 1963, 1975, 1987, 1999, 2011, 2023,

2035

The fourth position of Chinese zodiac is held by the rabbit that is talented, calm, creative and gentle. They are honourable, reserved and respect their privacy. They prefer to be their own counsel and only listen to their inner intuitions. They never complain about loneliness as they like their own company and personal time. In Chinese legend, the moon goddess Change’s had rabbit as her pet, making rabbit a symbol of pureness, amiability and auspiciousness. (12)

People born in rabbit year are friendly and inoffensive. They are loyal and dedicated towards their partners and while for friends they are kind-hearted, compassionated and in case of emergency one can count on them. They can effectively control their outwards display of emotions hence only close ones can understand their real feelings. Moreover, they are model parents who give proper education to their kids and establish a happy atmosphere. They are fated gentlemen with courteous manners in social settings while rabbit woman leaves

people with impression of elegant and gracious.

Rabbit tends to have peaceful existence by avoiding emotional overloads or dramatic turn of events. They keep things simple and enjoy the comforts. Generally, there are no major ups and down in their life and they progress at a steady pace. In Chinese folklore it is said rabbit have three exits to its burrow, allowing escape at its own will. They are wild in nature and love freedom. Also, they have excellent quality to heal from physical and psychological wound. They have active interest in healthy diet which ensures their long and healthy life. (6)(8)

Apart from their good qualities, rabbits can be aloof, secretive and self-centered. Their sensitive nature makes them get easily troubled by environment changes at work or home. They incline to escape reality. Likewise, they can be emotionally unstable, suspicious and might have difficulty in forming interpersonal relationships for long time.

Chinese Zodiac Rabbits

Years of the Rabbit:
(If born then, you're a Rabbit.)

...1915, 1927, 1939,
1951, 1963, 1975,
1987, 1999, 2011,
2023...

Lucky Things:

Lucky numbers

3

4

6

and numbers containing them (like 34 and 46)

Lucky colors

 pink

 red

 purple

 blue

Lucky flowers

 plantain lily

 jasmine

Lucky directions

east, south, northwest

Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers

1

7

8

and numbers containing them (like 17 and 87)

Unlucky colors

 dark brown

 dark yellow

 white

Unlucky directions

north, west, and southwest

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

Expressed in darkest form, rabbits can be paranoid, extremely introvert, self-absorbed and indecisive. ⁽⁶⁾

Favourable Career:

Gifted with creativity and art rabbit people can excel as musician, dancers, artist, and designers. Other good professions include teacher, priest, diplomat, philosopher, judge, and stockbroker and fashion model. ⁽⁶⁾⁽¹²⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Dog, Goat, Pig

Least compatible: Rat, Rooster, Snake

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in rabbit year are; Brad Pitt (actor), Albert Einstein (scientist), Benedict XVI (265th pope), Kate Winslet (actress), AdutAkech (model), Kendrick Lamar (singer), Queen Victoria.

DRAGON – lóng (龙)

Year: 1928, 1940, 1952, 1964, 1976, 1988, 2000, 2012, 2024, 2036

The fifth place of Chinese Zodiac is secured by the dragon symbolic of power, honour and success. A mythical creature of Chinese culture, that is considered a sign of good luck and vital health. It is the sign with greatest power and influence. They have power to influence, lead and to impress. They are highly ambitious for their dreams and goals, can deny any obstacle to reach the top, at times can work day-night to make things happen. Moreover, are symbolic of life and growth reflecting their generous nature. They tend to shine in all fields and do things which other can't do. ⁽⁶⁾

People born in dragon year are full of enthusiasm and energy, which keeps them always in motion and preoccupied. They are free and unpredictable soul thriving open space, adventures. They hate to take orders but like to give them which make them natural leaders. They are tenacious, captivating and full of Utopian ideas. For them life is an ocean of possibilities.

Unlike frightened dragon of western mythology, Chinese dragon is

Chinese Zodiac Dragons

Lucky numbers: 1, 6, 7 and numbers containing them (like 16 and 76)

Lucky colors: gold, silver, grayish white

Lucky flowers: bleeding-heart glory bower, dragon flowers

Lucky directions: east, north, south

Unlucky numbers: 3, 8 and numbers containing them (like 38 and 83)

Unlucky colors: blue, green

Unlucky directions: northwest

Years of the Dragon: (If born then, you're a Dragon.)
 ... 1916, 1928, 1940, 1952, 1964, 1976, 1988, 2000, 2012, 2024 ...

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

courageous and benevolent creature, which is willing to take risks. Confident and brave, dragon never seeks out for constant assurance. Lastly, they enjoy great popularity amongst friends. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

However, despite their good qualities a dragon person can be aggressive, short tempered and demanding which makes unapproachable by others. They can't face failures and are unwilling to admit their mistakes. Their authoritative nature can make them egoistic with belief of having right to rule. They can also be reckless, getting involved quickly without thinking about future. A restraint dragon can be impatient and intolerant. A dragon never forgets an insult and makes the most formidable enemies. Expressed in darkest form dragon can be stubborn, impulsive, complaining and quarrelsome. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favourable Career:

Dragon makes an excellent actor, politician, artist, prophet, lawyer, writer, teacher and business Owner, they perform best in independent professions. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rat, monkey, rooster

Least compatible: Ox, sheep, dog

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in dragon year are; Bruce Lee (Martial Artist and Actor), Vladimir Putin (Russian President), Adele (Singer-songwriter), Roald Dahl (author) and Jack Ma (entrepreneur).

SNAKE– shé(蛇)

Year: 1929, 1941, 1953, 1965, 1977, 1989, 2001, 2013, 2025,

2037.

The sixth place of Chinese zodiac is secured by the snake, which is known as little dragon in Chinese culture. Mostly this animal is considered evil and scares people however in Chinese tradition, it is respected creature and people still believe that a snake found in backyard is fortunate. Chinese godmother, Nüwa who is believed to have created humanity had body of a snake and head of a human. Snakes are patient, calculative and quietly powerful. They can easily attract others with their mysterious character and graceful behaviour. ⁽⁸⁾

They say little and are symbol of great wisdom with impeccable timing; always ready when it is time to act. Outwardly calm and calm and quiet, but passionate and lively from inside with long-term friends. They are determined with strong will to accomplish their goals. They tend to act according to their own judgement and are great thinkers. They are sign of unmatched physical beauty with flawless skin. These people are sophisticated and elegant in dress, speech and manner.

They prefer an orderly environment and require their utmost privacy. They are serious and devoted in a love relationship, cannot stand betrayal. Moreover, they possess ability to develop their sixth sense to point of divining. They enjoy pleasing others and adore ornamentation. ⁽⁶⁾

Apart from their good qualities, snake can be secretive and extravagant. They are often vain, stingy and a bit of selfish. Since they prefer to work alone, therefore are easily stressed. Their extravagance results in overspending. Expressed in darkest form, snake people can be

Chinese Zodiac Snakes

Lucky Things: Lucky Things:

Lucky numbers: 2 8 9 and numbers containing them (like 28 and 89)

Lucky colors: black, red, yellow

Lucky flowers: orchid, cactus

Lucky directions: W, E, SW, east, west, southwest

Years of the Snake:
(If born then, you're a Snake.)

... 1917, 1929, 1941, 1953, 1965, 1977, 1989, 2001, 2013, 2025...

Unlucky Things: Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers: 1 6 7 and numbers containing them (like 16 and 76)

Unlucky colors: brown, white, gold

Unlucky directions: NW, NE, northeast and northwest

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

vengefulness, lethargic, and have peculiar behaviour. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favourable Career:

Best professions for snake are; professor of philosophy, high-fashion model, public relations officer, psychiatrist, diplomat, ambassador, astrologers and fit well in any profession requiring the skill of divination. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Ox, Rooster

Least compatible: Tiger, horse, pig

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in snake year are; John F. Kennedy (35th US President), Mahatma Gandhi(nationalist), Martin Luther King Jr. (Civil Rights Activist), Howard Hughes (business magnate), J. K. Rowling (Author) and J. Paul Getty(industrialist).

HORSE– mǎ (马)

Year: 1930, 1942, 1954, 1966, 1978, 1990, 2002, 2014, 2026,

2038.

The seventh position in Chinese zodiac is held by horse, symbolic of enthusiasm and energy. People born in year horse are active, cheerful and easy-going. They have amazing zest for life and enjoy taking part in social activities. Extroverted talkative by nature, enjoy popularity among people and make a lot of friends. With great sense of humour, they are masters of repartee. With their great oration skills, they love to take centre stage and entertain people everywhere. Moreover, are strongest communicators in Chinese zodiac and are natural speakers. They love their freedom and independence.

They have strong desire for self-expression. A born leader, and always eager to help fellow mates. They are honourable in nature and are source of inspiration for others for their optimistic and assertive nature. They are physically attractive and swift with elegant dressing sense. They are most generous and hospitality conscious sign of the entire

Chinese Zodiac Horses

Lucky numbers
2 3 7
and numbers containing them (like 23 and 37)

Lucky colors
green
yellow

Lucky flowers
calla lily
jasmine

Lucky directions
east, west, southwest

Years of the Horse:
(If born then, you're a Horse.)

... 1918, 1930, 1942, 1954, 1966, 1978, 1990, 2002, 2014, 2026...

Unlucky numbers
1 5 6
and numbers containing them (like 15 and 65)

Unlucky colors
blue
white

Unlucky directions
north and northwest

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

Chinese zodiac. They cannot stand injustice and offer help to weak. Their talent and resolute spirit enables them to achieve great accomplishments. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

They love their family and children; they work hard to meet their wishes in return expect their respect towards them. They are straight-forward in communicating their preferences and are capable of making strong bonds with others. They are quick to forgive and forget and remain eternally positive.

Apart from horse's admirable qualities, they can be selfish, impatient and hot-headed. They can be self-centered and overly ambitious in their life. They can be overly possessive towards their partners. Lastly enjoy extravagant life which never allows them savings. Expressed in darkest form, horse can be aggressive, outspoken and overconfident. ⁽⁶⁾

Favourable Career:

The Horses are active and love exploring the world, which makes them good adventurers and tour guides. And they can always perform well in jobs like

writers, businessmen, artists, political leaders, public speaker, designer and athlete. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Tiger, goat, rabbit

Least compatible: Rat, ox, snake

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in horse year are; Jackie Chan (Actor), Kristen Stewart (Actress), Greta Thunberg (Climate Activist), Kobe Bryant (Basketball player), Nelson Mandela (activist and South-African president), Joe Biden (American president) and Neil Armstrong (astronaut).

GOAT- yáng (羊)

Year: 1931, 1943, 1955, 1967, 1979, 1991, 2003, 2015, 2027, 2039

The eighth position of Chinese zodiac is held by the Goat, who is gentle, calm and highly accomplished in arts. They constructively apply their intelligence to prevent any harm. They possess delicate thoughts, strong creativity, and perseverance and acquire great

Chinese Zodiac Goats

Years of the Goat:
(If born then, you're a Goat.)

... 1919, 1931, 1943, 1955, 1967, 1979, 1991, 2003, 2015, 2027 ...

Lucky Things:

Lucky numbers:
or numbers containing 2 and 7 (like 27 and 72)

Lucky colors: brown, red, purple

Lucky flowers: carnations, primroses

Lucky directions: north

Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers:
and numbers containing them (like 49 and 94)

Unlucky colors: blue, black

Unlucky directions: southwest

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

professional skills well. They have ability to sense the correct time to act. Those born under this year cannot live without beauty, and they strive for peacefulness. The easy going and adaptable Goat takes life at a leisurelier pace than others. ⁽⁶⁾

Although, they like to be in groups, but do not want to be the centre of attention. They are reserved and quiet. Being sensitive and sympathetic, they are always happy to give charities. They care about others' feelings and never mean to hurt them. Their upright personality makes them understand other's problems from various perspectives, especially of their friends and loved ones. Also, they attach great importance to their family and enjoy celebration of festivals and anniversaries with them. ⁽⁸⁾

Goats like to spend money on fashionable stuff which gives them an excellent look. In Chinese culture, the goat is considered auspicious since it was often used to offer sacrifices and pray to God for good fortune. It was also used as currency in ancient times, and thus it represents

wealth and lucky.

Apart from goat's admirable qualities, they can be very passive and hesitating, hence need strong support of partners in their work and life. They can also be naive and emotional. Moreover, can be clumsy at speech and be puzzled about life. Expressed in its darkest form, goat can be lazy, dependent on others, timid and impractical. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

Favourable Career:

Their natural talent in art and creativity makes some goat people successful painters, musicians, sculptor, beauticians, or writers. Other favourable career options include geologists, jewellers, dentists, chemists, veterinarians, scientists, doctors, teachers and public relations. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rabbit, Horse, Pig

Least compatible: Ox, Tiger, Dog

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in goat

year are; Ed Sheeran (Singer- Songwriter), Frida Kahlo(painter), Mark Twain(writer), Steve Jobs (Apple Co-founder), Lord Byron (poet), Kate Hudson(actress).

MONKEY–hóu(猴)

Year: 1932, 1944, 1956, 1968, 1980, 1992, 2004, 2016, 2028, 2040

The ninth position in Chinese zodiac is held by the Monkey who is smart, resourceful and mentally quick. In traditional Chinese culture, monkey is considered a mascot to pray for the good luck in career. In another Chinese legend, the most famous monkey is the Monkey King (Sun Wukong) born from a stone who was intelligent, brave, rebellious and talented. (8)

People born in monkey year are curious, eager to learn and have excellent skills of memorizing things. With their exceptional intelligence and efficient nature they can streamline any task with ability to figure out the shortest and easiest method to get it done.

Similarly, their hyperactivity can get tremendous amount of works done in no time also they are fast learners. At work, they take the first initiative and have amazing courage to face new challenges. They will devote themselves passionately to the work they are interested in, while be unresponsive to things they don't like. They hate boredom and their love for adventure, makes them seek a free and easy life with continuous new discoveries with countless of interests in life.

Out of all the 12 signs, Monkey has the most multi-coloured nature. They are high-spirited and outgoing enough to make an instant connection with just about everyone. Their humorous comments with perfect timing make them enjoyable and refreshing partners. Whenever there is a problem, monkey is the one who is capable in resolving the dilemma. They pay great attention to their family with being respectful to their parents and caring for kids. Lastly, they adapt impressively to diverse lifestyles and often have great grasping power for different languages. (6)

Chinese Zodiac Monkeys

Years of the Monkey:
(If born then, you're a Monkey.)

...1944, 1956, 1968,
1980, 1992, 2004,
2016...

Lucky Things:

Unlucky Things:

Lucky numbers

and numbers containing 4 and 9 (like 49 and 94)

Lucky colors

white
blue
gold

Lucky flowers

chrysanthemum
crape-myrtle

Lucky directions

north, northwest, west

Unlucky numbers

and numbers containing 2 and 7 (like 27 and 72)

Unlucky colors

red
pink

Unlucky directions

south, southeast

Source-www.chinahighlights.com

Apart from their good qualities, monkey can be opportunistic, impatient and arrogant. Their boasting may hinder them to make great success. Expressed in its darkest form, monkey can become trickery, disloyal, self-centered and can display immature behaviour. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favourable Career:

Monkeys are so multitalented that they have an excellent chance of succeeding in any career field like; Linguists, diplomats, journalists, entertainers, businessmen, professional athletes, stockbrokers, detectives, lawyers, stand-up comedian, travellers and screenwriter. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rat, Dragon, or Dog

Least compatible: Ox, Tiger, Pig

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in goat year are; Zayn Malik (Singer- songwriter), Kim Kardashian (TV Personality and Model), Julius Caesar(Roman dictator),

John Milton(poet), Will Smith (Actor) and Selena Gomez (Singer and Actress).

ROOSTER– jī (鸡)

Year: 1933, 1945, 1957, 1969, 1981, 1993, 2005, 2017, 2029, 2041

The tenth position of Chinese zodiac is secured by, the Rooster who is, pure minded, adaptable and always crave to do better. In ancient times there were no alarm clock, rooster used to help waking people up. Therefore, the first symbolic meaning of Chinese zodiac Rooster is punctuality, besides rooster calls before sunrise, so ancient Chinese people used to believe it had future prediction ability. Likewise, people born in this year have great prediction ability; they are great observers, farsighted and have clear plans for future. They work with great determination, hard work with their eyes set on their goals. ⁽⁸⁾

Generally well-dresses accompanied with elegant gestures and rich colours. They simply speak their mind and hate

Chinese Zodiac Roosters

Years of the Rooster:
(If born then, you're a Rooster.)

... 1933, 1945, 1957, 1969, 1981, 1993, 2005, 2017 ...

Lucky numbers

5
7
8

and numbers containing them (like 57 and 87)

Lucky colors

gold

brown

yellow

Lucky flowers

gladiola

cockscorn

Lucky directions

south, southeast

Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers

1
3
9

and numbers containing them (like 13 and 93)

Unlucky colors

red

Unlucky directions

east

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

hypocrisy. According to Chinese legend, Rooster is the sign with the utmost joys and the deepest sorrows, sometimes very rich, sometimes extremely poor, sometimes surrounded by room full of friends and sometimes all alone.

Often good at making friends and can easily adjust themselves into a new environment. They are at their best in crowd rather in intimate situations. With brilliant social skills, they possess sharp perspective into others' minds. They are frank. Open and loyal individuals. Their interest in reading makes them knowledgeable about a large variety of subjects with an excellent memory. However, they hardly display this knowledge openly. ⁽⁶⁾

Apart from their good qualities, a rooster can be vain, boastful and hypercritical. Often a bit eccentric, face difficult relationship with others. Failures hits them hard and are deeply disappointed when fail. Expressed in its darkest form, a rooster can be outspoken, selfish, arrogant, tactless, preoccupied with appearance and suspicious. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favourable Career:

The best careers for a Rooster are; collector, accountant, military officer/soldier, fireman, restaurant/cafe owner, high-fashion hairdresser, model, public relations specialist, financier. They can also be a tour guide or an actor/actress, because they rarely feel shy when speaking or performing in public. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Ox, Dragon, Snake

Least compatible: Rat, rabbit, Horse

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in goat year are; Jennifer Aniston(Actress), Ariana Grande (singer), Chris Evans (actor), Roger Federer(Tennis Champion), Prince Philip, Benjamin Franklin(founding father of US), Larry King (television host) and Meghan Markle (Duchess of Sussex and Former Actress).

DOG– gǒu (狗)

Year: 1934, 1946, 1958, 1970, 1982, 1994, 2006, 2018, 2030, 2042

The eleventh position of Chinese zodiac is held by dog, which is alert and has a strong sense of justice. Chinese people consider dog as an auspicious animal. If a dog randomly comes to a house, it symbolizes the coming of fortune with it. In Chinese legend, God Erlang had a loyal dog

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

partner who helped him in capturing monsters. The most important features of a Dog are loyalty and honesty. They are extremely loyal towards their loved one and extremely fierce towards their enemies. Those born in Dog year protect those weaker than them.

Being pure and virtuous, they are wonderful friends, honest lovers and reliable families. They never turn their backs in times of need. Hence make lifetime friends. Likewise, they prefer socializing with few close friends only. Large social gatherings with unfamiliar people and surroundings make them uncomfortable. Similarly, they care about their families deeply. Most distinguishing trait of this sign is lack of desire for personal gain, especially financially. ⁽⁸⁾

Chinese Zodiac Dogs

Years of the Dog:
(If born then, you're a Dog.)

...1922, 1934, 1946,
1958, 1970, 1982,
1994, 2006, 2018, ...

Lucky Things: Lucky Things:

Lucky numbers: 3 4 9
and numbers containing them
(like 39 and 49)

Lucky colors: green
red
purple

Lucky flowers: rose
cymbidium orchids

Lucky directions: NE
E
S
east, south, and northeast

Unlucky Things: Unlucky Things:

Unlucky numbers: 1 6 7
and numbers containing them
(like 17 and 67)

Unlucky colors: blue
white
gold

Unlucky directions: SE
southeast

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

They possess high principles, hate injustice and inequities and strive to correct them. They can't stand anyone with greed for power, money or disloyal. Moreover, they are trustworthy, non-materialistic and have an attractive personality. Dog is a "keen and penetrating observer." Brimming with life, they seek more than excitement of new experiences; they are interested in understanding the meaning of things and promoting social awareness.

Apart from their admirable qualities, dog can agitate, secretive and suspicious. Their criticality can sometimes make a sharp criticism of others. As dogs are not good at communicating their feelings. Therefore, others have impression that they have a stubborn personality. Expressed in darkest form, a dog can become anxious, paranoid, depressed and have dependent behaviour. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Favourable Career:

Dog can be successful as a reformer, teacher, religious leader, judge, behind-the-scenes advisor, social worker. Other

favourable options include; critics, writers, poets, philosophers, and moralists, teacher and doctor. ⁽⁶⁾⁽⁸⁾

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rabbit, Tiger

Least compatible: Dragon, Goat, Rooster

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in goat year are; Mother Teresa (Catholic Missionary), Michael Jackson (Pop star), Donald Trump (45th president), Stan lee (comic book artist), Akira Kurosawa (Film Director and Screenwriter) and Justin Bieber (Pop star).

PIG-zhū (猪)
Year: 1935, 1947, 1959, 1971,
1983, 1995, 2007, 2019, 2031,
2043

The twelfth position of Chinese zodiac is held by the Pig, which represents prosperity and luck from the ancient times. They are docile, gentle-hearted and forgiving sign. They accept others as they are and understand that human nature is controlled by fate. They

are wise and highly intelligent; prefer to be passive observer rather than an active participant in their social life.

People born in pig year are diligent, compassionate, and generous. They have great concentration skills, once a goal is set, they will work tirelessly and sincerely to achieve it. Their great sense of responsibility helps finish what they were engaged in. These people love the comforts of life, especially with adequate affection. They like to surround themselves with beauty, liberty, fresh air, and plenty of greenery. Moreover, possess a unique sense of dry humour. (6)

Known to be thoughtful and knowledgeable, the Pig chooses few friends, however, remains loyal for life. In bad times one can always count on them for help. These souls are tolerant companions with patience and understanding hence enjoys long-standing relationships. They are affectionate, openhearted and genuine. Though they hardly seek help from others but will never refuse to give others a helping hand and would never plan to harm others. (4)

Apart from their good qualities, a pig can be passive, self-indulgent and lazy. They can suffer from gullibility and can easily trust, as they assume people are pure-hearted like them but sometimes people take advantage of them and can trick them. Expressed in its darkest form, pig can be extremely innocent, defencelessness, lack competitive spirit and be overly reliant on physical or material comforts. (6)(8)

Favourable Career:

The best occupations for Pig people are veterinarian, breeder, forester, teacher, civil servant, policeman, doctor, professor filmmakers, writers, poets, painters, entrepreneurs and artist. Agriculture, animal husbandry and medical are suitable fields for them. (6)(8)

Compatibility:

Most compatible: Rabbit, Tiger, goat
Least compatible: Snake, monkey

Famous Personalities:

Some of the famous people born in goat year are; Tenzin Gyatso (14th Dalai Lama), Elon Musk (Entrepreneur), Chris Hemsworth (actor), Hillary Clinton

Chinese Zodiac Pigs

Lucky Things:

Years of the Pig:
(If born then, you're a Pig.)

...1923, 1935, 1947, 1959, 1971, 1983, 1995, 2007, 2019, 2031...

Unlucky Things:

Lucky numbers

2 5 8

and numbers containing them (like 25 and 58)

Lucky colors

 yellow
 gray
 brown
 gold

Lucky flowers

 hydrangea
 daisy

Lucky directions

east, southwest

Unlucky numbers

1 7

and numbers containing them (like 17 and 71)

Unlucky colors

 red
 blue
 green

Unlucky directions

southeast

Source: www.chinahighlights.com

(politician), William Golding (Novelist) and Kendall Jenner (model).

Chinese Zodiac Relevance in Today's Time

Chinese speak of 2 faces that make our personality. The first is Xian tian, the inherited "temperament", these are the attributes we already have when we come to life. The second is Hou tian, the acquired "character" which is determined by our choices and conduct. Hence Chinese zodiac determines the temperament of the person. (6)

The Chinese zodiac is an important element of the Chinese culture. These signs have been in practice from ancient times. Fortune tellers have been using them for centuries to predict the fame and fortune of innumerable commoners and emperors. Even today, millions of Chinese people believe in these predictions and that ruling animal of one's birth year has a profound influence on their personality and destiny. Traditionally, this animal resides in one's heart and can interact positively or negatively with others. ⁽¹⁾⁽¹¹⁾

In fact, a lot of Chinese people still consider birth year when making decisions about relationships, marriages, whether their personality is compatible with potential partners or not. They believe that having a deep knowledge about one's Chinese zodiac sign and horoscope can actually help forecast problems in the coming month or year and improve your life, rather than succumbing to what fate will decide for them. ⁽¹²⁾

CONCLUSION

The twelve animals that appear on the Chinese zodiac calendar i.e., a rat, ox,

tiger, rabbit, dragon, snake, horse, goat, monkey, rooster, dog and pig mare the topic of innumerable legends rooted in Chinese mythology. Each symbolic of certain trait and qualities. They help an individual to get a general self-awareness about their nature, careers, partners and destiny so that one can make better decisions about their life and reach up to their highest potential. Although this knowledge is thousands of years old, even today it is successfully practiced across the Chinese nation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Personalities of Chinese Zodiac (2016) by Liu ,Tang Hsuan (Rochester Institute of Technology)
- [2] The Twelve Animals: An interactive guide to the Chinese zodiac Signs (2011) by Chen, Yanzi (Rochester Institute of Technology)
- [3] Animal Symbolism of Trademarks and trade characters by Kim, Hyun-Jee (Seoul National University)
- [4] Chinese Astrology: Exploring the Eastern Zodiac Author Name: Wu, Shelly
- [5] Liu, T. H. (2016). Personalities of the Chinese zodiac Thesis. Rochester Institute of Technology. Google Scholar. <https://scholarworks.rit.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=10125andcontext=theses>. Accessed on 21 September 2021.
- [6] Wu, Shelly, 2005, Chinese Astrology: Exploring the Eastern Zodiac. Red Wheel/Weiser. Pdf drive. Accessed on 5 October 2021
- [7] Chen, Yanzi, 2011, "The Twelve animals: An Interactive guide to the Chinese zodiac signs" Thesis. Rochester Institute of Technology. Google Scholar. <https://scholarworks.rit.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7102andcontext=theses>. Accessed on 5 October 2021.
- [8] <https://www.goway.com/travel-information/asia/china/chinese-zodiac/>. Date accessed 2 October 2021.

- [9] <https://www.chinahighlights.com/travelguide/chinese-zodiac/>. Date accessed 2 October 2021.
- [10] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chinese_zodiac. Date accessed 2 October 2021.
- [11] <http://www.vam.ac.uk/content/articles/c/chinese-zodiac-ox/>. Date accessed 20 November
- [12] https://www.travelchinaguide.com/intro/social_customs/zodiac/. Date accessed 20
- [13] <https://www.oprahdaily.com/life/a35119928/chinese-zodiac-signs/> Date accessed 20 November 2021.
- [14] <https://sg.finance.yahoo.com/news/chinese-zodiac-best-financial-outlook-093932953.html>. Date accessed 20 November 2021.
- [15] <https://studycli.org/chinese-zodiac/>. Date accessed 20 November 2021. <https://depts.washington.edu/triolive/quest/2007/TTQ07030/culture.html#:~:text=The%20importance%20of%20the%20zodiac,were%20represented%20with%20each%20animal.andtext=In%20general%2C%20the%20zodiac%20provides,how%20people%20live%20their%20lives.> Date accessed 20 November 2021.
- [16] <http://idp.bl.uk/4DCGI/education/astronomy/astrology.html>. Date accessed 1 December 2021.